

The Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on the Performance of Student Startup Higher Education in Jabodetabek

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Abstract:- This research focuses on the dimensions and indicators of effectiveness, curriculum and learning models, facilitation, the role of the government and the private sector in entrepreneurship education that affect the performance of student startups as measured by indicators of income, sales volume and marketing area. IPB University, University of Indonesia, National University and Esa Unggul University in 2016-2020. This research is a quantitative descriptive study using statistical analysis. The results of this study indicate that the effect of entrepreneurship education (X) on the successful performance of student startup (Y) is 0.0%. Positive regression coefficient of 0.142. This explains that if increase in entrepreneurship education (X) by 1 units, then the performance of student startup (Y) will increase by 0.142 units.

Keywords:- Entrepreneurship Education, Student Startup Performance, Jabodetabek.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of a nation into a developed and modern country must be supported by superior and competent human resources. A condition in which the human resources of a country are seen as being able to support development and economic growth if the number of people in that country is at least 2 percent of the people into entrepreneurship or entrepreneurs as expressed by McClelland (Van Nostrand: 1961) in Sutrisna Dewi (2017: 29).

Technology-supported education can accelerate the modernization process at the individual, family and community levels. Today, knowledge, skills, technology, and innovation can be absorbed and disseminated quickly and easily through modern education.

Data relating to the implementation of entrepreneurship and student startup lectures in universities which are research findings at the University of IPB, the number of innovations and businesses produced by IPB during 2014-2018 was 2014=12 innovations, 2015=45 innovations, 2016=67 innovation, in 2017 = 73 innovations and in 2018 = 65 innovations. (IPB Strategic Plan 2019-2023). Meanwhile, the findings of field data at the University of Indonesia The data obtained that in the 2015-2019 period, the Directorate of

Innovation and Business Incubator, University of Indonesia gave birth to 94 student startups, in 2015=14 tenants, 2016=14 tenants, 2017=21 tenants, 2018=22 tenants and 2019=23 tenants (UI Magazine, July 2019).

The data on the two universities shows that there are still a small number of student startup students who are accompanied by university entrepreneurial incubators. What about private campuses like the National University? Of course, when compared to other campuses such as Bina Nusantara University, Prasetya Mulya University Tarumanagara University, it is still far from being expected to produce and realize the number of entrepreneurship in Indonesia.

Based on research conducted by (Cukier & Kon, 2018) establish a Startup Ecosystem Conceptual Framework that describes how startup relationships with various variables are found that Education does not have a direct effect on Startups and does not as the crow flies influence Technologies, by oneself to the proportion that it fix up with provision consciousness in Technologies that chalk up a orchestrate and substantial chain reaction on Startups. instruction furthermore has a orchestrate and substantial chain reaction on Entrepreneurs which as the crow flies and importantly lay hold of Startups.

This study is different from previous studies because it focuses more on the chain reaction of entrepreneurship instruction on the performance of student startups at universities in Greater Jakarta and what are the factors that influence the performance of student startups at universities in Greater Jakarta. Student startup performance is measured by indicators revenue, sales volume, and marketing area. So the researchers conducted a study with the title: The Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on the Performance of College Student Startups in Greater Jakarta.

II. METHODS

The contemplate was conducted to influence the chain reaction of entrepreneurship instruction on the accomplishment of student startups at universities in Greater Jakarta-tabek. This research is a quantitative descriptive research where Sulisty (2006) explains that descriptive research can be done quantitatively so that it can be done statistic analysis.

Collection method data conducted in this study by using tools questionnaire. Questionnaire is a question structured which is filled in by respondent or filled in by the interviewer who read the questions and then record the answer given (Sulisty, 2006). Type The questionnaire used is closed questionnaire where the respondent asked to answer questions and answer by choosing from a number of alternatives.

The population of this research is all student startups at universities in Jabodetabekare 2,459 student startups and the determination of the sample is done using the *random sampling where each element* population has an equal chance to be selected as a sample (Kuncoro, 2013).

Next, to determine the number of samples, this study admits on the opinion of Roscoe (1975) in Sekaran (2003) which interprets that regulations of pollex in deciding the proportion exemplification be required to be in a superior way than 30 and few than 500 respondents to receive euphemistic pre-owned in indefinite classifications of evaluation so the character of representatives is 10 intervals or bounteous than the character of variables in the contemplate multivariate. *Therefore, the number* the sample in this study is 100 samples selected at random from selected universities are: University of IPB, University of Indonesia, National University and Esa Unggul University.

Validity and reliability testing is done using software SPSS to find out that the testdone really measure that should be measured and consistent. The data obtained in this studywere then processed and analyzed. The analytic disposition euphemistic pre-owned therein contemplate is descriptive psychoanalysis with a simple one-dimensional retrogression disposition with the undermentioned equalization model: $Y = a + bX$.

Where:

Y= Student statup performance at University in Jabodetabek

a = Constant

b = Regression Coefficient

X = Entrepreneurship Education

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the findings of research conducted on 100 respondents who are student startups at universities in Jabodetabek whose research locus was carried out as many as 30student startups at the University of IPB, 30 student startups at the University of Indonesiaand 20 student startups at the National University and 20 student startups at Esa University. The results of research and analysis of research results can be stated as superior, as explained below.

This contemplate was conducted to influence the chain reaction of entrepreneur-ship education (X) on the performance of student startups at universities in Greater Jakarta (Y). The method used is simple linear regression with a maximum error rate (alpha) of 5%. The drug-addicted changeable on the consequences of the regression evaluation is the performance of student.

Startup (Y), the independent variable is entrepreneurship education (X). Regression modelbased on the consequences of the psychoanalysis in above are: $Y = 15,439 + 0.142X$.

The mentoring regression coefficient (X) is 0.142 with a t value of 5.143 (more than in a superior way than t tabularise 1.994) or the expenditure of significance 0.000 (smaller than alpha 5% or 0.050) which means that mentoring variable (X) has an effect significant to start-up success business (Y) at an error rate of 5%. The significance value (p-value) is 0.000 indicates that the risk of error decision making in states that there is an influence entrepreneurship education (X) on the success of student startup performance (Y) is 0.0%. Positive regression coefficient of 0.142 explains that if increase in entrepreneurship education (X) by 1 unit, so the accomplishment of undergraduate beginning (Y) testament aggrandizement by 0.142 constituents.

Table 1. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig. t	Information
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	15,439	1,403		11.090	.000	Significant
Entrepreneurship Education	.142	.036	.470	5.143	.000	Significant
t table (t5%, 98)	1994					
R	.470					
R-square	.222					
F count	26,353					
Sig. F	.000					
F table (F5%,1.98)	3.948					

The coefficient of determination (R²) is used to measure until when the model's qualification to account for alteration of the drug-addicted changeable (Y), patch remainder is explained by over-the-counter variables elsewhere representation. According to Ghozali (2006), basic weakness of application the coefficient of steadfastness is one-sided in relation to the character of self-governing variables that integrated into the model. Every augmentation of individual self-governing changeable, then R2 definitely increases no matter does this variable have an effect? significantly to the variable dependent. Therefore, the value of R Square in this study used to evaluate the best regression model.

Table 2. Coefficient of Steadfastness

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of The Estimate
1	470 ^a	.222	.214	2.60594

From Table 2 coefficient of Determination it is shown that the expenditure of R straightforward of 0. 222 or 22. This complication have in mind that the student startup performance variable (Y) is explained by 22.2% by the entrepreneurship education variable (X), patch the outstanding 77. 8% is explained by over-the-counter variables or self-governing variables elsewhere the regression equation.

Possibility investigation is finished by victimisation of the t evaluation where t enumeration is 5.143 (see table 1) and greater from t table 1,994 so that the test the hypothesis for H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. These findings, empirically, shows that entrepreneurship education positive effect on student startup performance (table 1). This matter proves that the performance of student startups at universities in Jabodetabek influenced by the entrepreneurship education process.

This contemplate magnitudes the chain reaction of entrepreneurship education (X) on the accomplishment of student startups at universities in Greater Jakarta (Y). The process of entrepreneurship education in universities can be seen from the learning of entrepreneurship courses that are required in every university. Apart from lecturing, universities are also required to have a business incubator that accompanies students who have high intentions to start a business or have a student startup.

Based on the concepts, theories and research explanations from Alfred Suci, Bambang Suroto, Hadiyati (2015), the dimensions and indicators of the entrepreneurship education variable include the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education, curriculum and entrepreneurship learning models, facilitation, the role of the government and the private sector in entrepreneurship education. While the performance of student startups is measured by the dimensions and indicators of income, sales volume, and performance marketing area (Keeh, Tat, Nguyen, and Ping, 2007).

The consequences of this contemplate established that the cognitive semantics of entrepreneurship instruction is a individual of the constituents that influence performance of student startups at universities in Greater Jakarta. In the process of implementing entrepreneurship education or which is a very important activity in supporting the performance of student startups, it is influenced by factors of effectiveness, curriculum and learning models, facilitation, the role of the government and the private sector in entrepreneurship education.

This evaluation is in occupation with and backs up the evaluation conducted Alfred Suci, Bambang Suroto, Hidayati, (2015), Yunsoo Shim and Jounghae Seo (2020), Chang-Ryong Ko and Jong-In An (2019), Euna Lee, Yunsoo Shim and Jounghae Seo (2019), Pasit Potjanjaruwit (2018), Andre Soekanto and Carolina Novi Mustikarini (2017), Aryan Eka Prastya Nugraha and Novika Wahyuhastuti (2017), Christina Yanita Setyawati (2016) and Juha Sauk-konen (2017) which relate to the constituents that consequence the accomplishment of undergraduate startups or business startup performance.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Supported on the consequences of the evaluation and give-and-take of the evaluation that has been described, it buoy be terminated that the effect of entrepreneurship education (X) on the successful performance of student startup (Y) is 0.0%. Positive regression coefficient of 0.142 explains that if increase in entrepreneurship education (X) by 1 unit, so the accomplishment of undergraduate beginning (Y) testament aggrandizement by 0. 142 units.

This shows that the entrepreneurship education process seen from the dimensions and indicators of effectiveness, curriculum and learning models, facilitation, the role of the government and the private sector in entrepreneurship education has an effect on the success and improvement of student startup performance as measured by indicators of income, sales volume, and marketing area.

This research uses data collected from respondents who is a student startup from selected universities in Greater Jakarta, namely IPB University, University of Indonesia, National University and Esa Unggul University. Obstacles and limitations of research faced by researchers are due to limited time, cost as well met some respondents experienced the difficulty in recalling the entrepreneurship education process that he has taken and the mentoring carried out by the university business incubator he has experienced, because the majority of respondents are students at the end of the lecture who are running a startup business (student startup).

The findings of this study indicate the need to find a more perfect method of entrepreneurship education and the need to choose teachers who really understand the effectiveness, curriculum and learning models, facilitation, the role of the government and the private sector in entrepreneurship education to improve student startup performance.

Supported on the discoveries of this glance at it is recommended for universities to examine this research further and for other researchers to conduct research using other variables to determine their effect on student startup performance.

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